

Effect of Hydroxyurea Therapy on Sickle Cell Patients with Emphasis on Biochemical & Hematological Parameters in a Tertiary Care Centre of Eastern Part of Chhattisgarh State

Soni LK¹, Behra A², Mane SK³, Bhardwaj AK⁴, Uraon HK⁵, Minj MK⁶

¹Associate professor, Department of Pediatrics, Late Shri Lakhiram, Agrawal Memorial Govt. Medical College Raigarh (C.G.), India

²Associate professor, Department of Skin & VD, Late Shri Lakhiram, Agrawal Memorial Govt. Medical College Raigarh (C.G.), India

³Associate Professor, Department of Surgery, Late Shri Lakhiram, Agrawal Memorial Govt. Medical College Raigarh (C.G.), India

⁴Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Pt. J.N.M. Medical College Raipur (C.G.), INDIA

⁵Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Late Shri Lakhiram, Agrawal Memorial Govt. Medical College Raigarh (C.G.), India

⁶Professor, Department of Pathology, Late Shri Lakhiram, Agrawal Memorial Govt. Medical College Raigarh (C.G.), India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Shobhita Kumar Mane

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Abstract:

Introduction: Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) is an inherited disorder of Hemoglobin. SCD is highly prevalent in many parts of India including Chhattisgarh & predominantly affects the tribal & under privileged sections of the society. In SCD Adult Hemoglobin gets polymerized & alters its Physio-Chemical properties manifested by change in the normal shape of RBC to shape of a sickle.

Aim: To compare the Hematological & Biochemical parameters in sickle cell homozygous patients (SS) with & without Hydroxyurea therapy.

Materials and Methods: A case control prospective study was carried out in the Department of Pediatrics, Surgery, Biochemistry & Pathology, Late Shri Lakhiram Agrawal Memorial Government Medical College & Associated Sant Baba Guru Ghasidas Ji Memorial Govt. hospital Raigarh, Chhattisgarh.

Results: Total 120 subjects in this study were categorized into four groups 30 (AA), 30 (AS), 30 (SCD with HU therapy) & 30 (SCD without HU therapy). Hb concentration, Hb F level, RBC count, RBC indices like MCV & MCH levels, Electrolyte Potassium levels were significantly improved in SCD with HU therapy groups as compared to SCD without HU therapy groups. The improvements were statically significant.

Conclusions: We found a significant improvement of Hb concentration, RBC count, MCV, MCH & HbF level with decrease reticulocyte count in SCD with HU therapy groups as compared to SCD without HU therapy.

Keywords: (HbF) Fetal hemoglobin, (SS) Homozygous SCD, (AS) Heterozygous SCD, Hydroxyurea (HU), (SCD) Sickle cell disease..

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Introduction

Sickle cell disease is the most common single genetic mutation found in human beings. It results from a single base-pair mutation in the gene for the Beta-Globin subunit of adult hemoglobin HbA. This happens due to substitution of nucleotide Adenine by Thymine (GAG to GTG) on the short arm of Chromosome 11 resulting in the replacement of Glutamic acid by Valine in the Sixth Amino acid position of β globin chain. Sickle cell disease is transmitted as an autosomal recessive trait [1]. In India SCD is common in Andhra Pradesh, Maharashtra, Karnataka, Kerala,

Chhattisgarh, Tamilnadu, Uttar Pradesh, and Gujarat. In Chhattisgarh, Sickle cell disease is common in Central & Northern part i.e. a few district like Sarguja, Raigarh, Jashpur, Mahasamund & Korea etc. In Caste-wise distribution of SCD in Chhattisgarh, the disease is more prevalent in the Other Backward Communities (OBC) like Teli, Agharia, Kurmi, Kolta, Kumhar, Scheduled Tribe (ST) communities of Halba, Gond, Binjhar, & Scheduled Caste (SC) communities of Satnami, Ghasia, Gada, and Mahar etc [2].

Hemoglobin-F is an effective inhibitor of HbS polymerization. Hydroxyurea is used to increase HbF synthesis and improve the clinical course of sickle cell disease patients. A high level of Fetal hemoglobin (HbF) in SCD correlates with increased life expectancy and a decrease in the incidence of vasoocclusive crises [3].

Sickle Cell Anemia erythropoiesis is manifested by Reticulocytosis. In SCA, increased numbers of immature reticulocytes are released into the circulation to help maintain adequate tissue oxygenation. Sickle Cell Anemia is apparent very early in life (from 10 weeks of infancy) in SS pattern and this anemia is underlined by hemolytic process which is evident with a rising Reticulocyte count [4,5].

Hydroxyurea (HU) therapy has been found to increase in the level of fetal hemoglobin (HbF), mean cell volume (MCV) & greatly improve the clinical state of homozygous sickle cell disease (SS-SCD) patients [6,7]. Hydroxyurea therapy in children and adolescents with sickle cell disease, the increase HbF levels achieved during treatment were associated with survival of erythrocytes, resulting in a decrease in the frequency and severity of vaso-occlusive crisis [8].

Routine laboratory test includes complete blood count (CBC), RBC indices, Reticulocyte count and Biochemistry parameter to evaluate complications like Vaso-Occlusive & other crisis due to sickle cell disease & also helpful for management of sickle cell disease.

Aims & Objectives

1. To compare the Hematological parameters like Hb, RBC, TLC, Reticulocyte count & RBC indices of homozygous sickle cell patients (SS) under Hydroxyurea therapy and homozygous sickle cell patients (SS) without Hydroxyurea therapy.
2. To compare the HbF levels of homozygous SCD patients taking Hydroxyurea in comparison to homozygous SCD patients without Hydroxyurea therapy.

Materials and Methods

This study was done in the Department of Biochemistry, sickle cell unit, Department of Surgery & Department of Pediatrics of Late Shri Lakhiram Agrawal Memorial Medical College associated Sant Baba Guru Ghasidas Ji Memorial Government Hospital Raigarh Chhattisgarh for a period of 2022 to 2023, after getting approval by the Institutional Ethics Committee. The study age group comprised 10 – 40 yrs. of 80 subjects. The group was divided into three subgroups, Normal Controls AA (20), Sickle Cell trait AS (20) and SCD homozygous patients SS (40). SCD patients' subgroup comprised of further two subgroups of 20

subjects each, viz., those on Hydroxyurea therapy & that not on Hydroxyurea therapy.

Inclusion Criteria

- Homozygous sickle cell disease (SS) patients without Hydroxyurea therapy.
- Homozygous sickle cell disease (SS) patients with continuing Hydroxyurea therapy for at least more than one month at a dose of 10 mg/kg body weight single dose every alternate day.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with any other associated Haemoglobinopathy or Blood Dyscrasias.
- Patients with history of discontinued Hydroxyurea therapy.
- Pregnant & Lactating women.

Methodology

After getting written informed consent, 5ml of venous blood was collected from all subjects by phlebotomy in two vials. 1st 3 ml in a plain vial for biochemical parameters & 2nd 2 ml in a vial containing 0.05 ml of EDTA as anticoagulant for hematological parameters estimation. Subjects were identified as sickle cell trait (AS) and SCD (SS) through Electrophoresis. Hematological parameters like Hemoglobin level, RBC count, total leukocyte count (TLC), MCV, MCH, MCHC, were measured by using Horiba-ABX Pentra XL 5 Part Differential Automated Hematology cell counter & HbF level by D-10 Bio-Rad HPLC. Biochemical parameters were measured by using Agappe Full biochemical auto-analyzer. Reticulocyte count was measured by 2 peripheral smears prepared & stained by Brilliant cresyl blue (Supravital stain). Reticulocyte count was calculated as percentage after manually studying at least 1000 RBCs under microscope.

Statistical Analysis: The data was presented in the form of percentages, frequencies and figures such as tables, charts and graphs. Data & Statistical analysis was done using SPSS. Correlation between Hemoglobin, HbF & Reticulocyte was calculated. ANOVA and Post – hoc Bonferroni test were used to analyze the observed data. P value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The mean age in the different study group was (AA) 19.12±3.43, sickle cell heterozygous (AS) 18.14±1.67, SCD homozygous (SS) without HU therapy 18.54±2.23 and SCD homozygous (SS) with HU therapy groups 16.56±3.23 years. In table (1) shows HbF level in AA, AS, SCD without hydroxyurea therapy and SCD with hydroxyurea therapy different groups was found to be 0.68 ± 0.32%, 2.65 ± 1.87%, 19.06 ± 3.6% and 23.42 ± 5.24% respectively. Applying ANOVA the

difference between four groups was found to be statistically significant p value <0.005. Haematological parameters like hemoglobin concentration in (AA) group were 12.83 ± 2.28 , (AS) 11.6 ± 2.29 , SS without HU therapy 8.32 ± 1.24 , SS with HU therapy 11.75 ± 1.70). SS patients without HU therapy had a hemoglobin concentration significantly lower than the AA & AS groups. Difference in hemoglobin concentration between the AA, AS, SS without HU therapy & SS with HU therapy groups was found to be statistically significant (p value<0.005). RBC count in (AA) 4.18 ± 0.56 , (AS) 4.10 ± 0.50 , SS without HU therapy 3.12 ± 0.64 , & SS with HU therapy 3.86 ± 0.68 .

Mean RBC count SCD Hydroxyurea therapy group was found to be significantly higher SCD without Hydroxyurea therapy groups p value <0.005. RBC indices like MCV level in the AA, AS, SCD without Hydroxyurea therapy and SCD with Hydroxyurea therapy different groups was found to be 85.48 ± 8.60 , 77.12 ± 9.64 , 76.34 ± 9.12 , 82.32 ± 7.46 & MCH concentration in the AA (31.18 ± 3.19) AS (26.54 ± 3.78) SS without HU therapy (25.28 ± 3.46) SS with HU therapy (26.79 ± 2.73). Applying ANOVA the difference between the values of MCV & MCH for four groups was found to be statistically significant (p value <0.005). MCHC in the AA, AS, SCD without Hydroxyurea therapy and SCD with Hydroxyurea therapy

different groups was found to be respectively, 33.56 ± 1.76 , 32.86 ± 1.24 , 30.64 ± 1.54 , 29.24 ± 1.43 . Applying ANOVA the difference between the values of MCHC for four groups was found to be not statistically significant p value 0.5013. Total leukocyte count in the AA, AS, SCD without Hydroxyurea therapy and SCD with Hydroxyurea therapy different groups was found to be respectively 7.56 ± 2.50 , 7.14 ± 2.10 , 11.08 ± 3.68 , 9.02 ± 3.64 .

Applying ANOVA the difference between the values of Total leukocyte count for four groups was found to be not statistically significant p value 0.625. Reticulocyte count 1.54 ± 0.18 in (AA groups), 1.89 ± 0.34 in (AS groups), 2.67 ± 0.15 in (SS without HU therapy groups) and 1.60 ± 0.13 in (SS with HU therapy). Applying ANOVA the difference between the values of reticulocyte count for four groups was found to be statistically significant (p value <0.001). Serum electrolyte sodium in the (AA) 133.62 ± 1.71 , (AS) 132.52 ± 1.38 , (SS without HU therapy) 131.47 ± 1.77 , (SS with HU therapy) 132.36 ± 1.25 & similarly potassium level was 3.55 ± 0.17 , 3.49 ± 0.14 , 3.88 ± 0.39 , 3.38 ± 0.13 respectively AA, AS SS without HU therapy & SS with HU therapy. Applying ANOVA the difference between the values of electrolyte sodium & potassium for four groups only potassium level was found to be statistically significant (p value <0.005).

Table 1: Haematological & Biochemical parameters in different groups.

Parameters	AA	AS	SS with-out HU therapy	SS with HU therapy	P value
Age	19.12±3.43	18.14±1.67	18.54±2.23	16.56±3.23	0.003****
Hb (g %)	12.83 ± 2.28	11.6 ± 2.29	8.32 ± 1.24	11.75 ± 1.70	<0.005***
RBC count (million cell/mL)	4.18 ± 0.56	4.10 ± 0.50	3.12 ± 0.64	3.86 ± 0.68	<0.005***
TLC (cell/mm ³)	7.56 ± 2.50	7.14 ± 2.10	11.08 ± 3.68	9.02 ± 3.64	<0.625
MCV (fL)	85.48 ± 8.60	77.12 ± 9.64	76.34 ± 9.12	82.32 ± 7.46	<0.005***
MCH (pg)	31.18 ± 3.19	26.54 ± 3.78	25.28 ± 3.46	26.79 ± 2.73	<0.005***
MCHC (g/dl)	31.96 ± 1.82	31.37 ± 1.50	29.7 ± 1.53	31.63 ± 1.40	0.5908
HbF (%)	0.68 ± 0.32	2.65 ± 1.87	19.06 ± 3.6	23.42 ± 5.24	<0.005***
Reticulocyte count (%)	1.54 ± 0.18	1.89 ± 0.34	2.67 ± 0.15	1.60 ± 0.13	<0.001***
Sodium (mEq/L)	133.62 ± 1.71	132.52 ± 1.38	131.47 ± 1.77	132.36 ± 1.25	<0.1298
Potassium (mEq/L)	3.55 ± 0.17	3.49 ± 0.14	3.88 ± 0.39	3.38 ± 0.13	<0.005***

Discussion

This study evaluated the Reticulocyte count, HbF level, hematological and Biochemical parameters in sickle cell disease patients with Hydroxyurea therapy & without Hydroxyurea therapy.

In SCD patient's, hydroxyurea therapy increased HbF levels, reduced frequency of Acute Chest Syndrome, reduced blood transfusions, hospitalizations, and possibly improved survival. HU therapy was safe with no clinically significant hematopoietic depression requiring cessation of

drug therapy. In 2010 Harminder Singh et al, studied effective control of sickle cell disease with hydroxyurea therapy & found significant increase in HbF% & MCV after one year treatment with HU in sickle cell disease patients. We also find increase HbF and MCV level in SCD patients taking HU [9]. In 1996 Charache S, Barton FB, et al study reported rise of hemoglobin level, HbF & MCV after HU treatment.

Our study has also shown that Hydroxyurea improves HbF, Hb, MCV & MCH in SCD patients. Other parameters like TLC, MCHC & electrolyte

sodium have not shown any significant difference between the groups on therapy and that not on Hydroxyurea therapy [10].

In 2014 Patel et al. significant increase in serum level of Hb F, total hemoglobin (Hb), MCV and MCH after treatment with hydroxyurea of sickle cell disease patients [11]. Similarly in our study has also shown significant improvement of HbF, MCV & MCH in SCD patients undergoing HU therapy. This investigation has several limitations. As the size of sample included in this study was small, the findings may be validated using a larger data.

Conclusion

This study found an increase HbF% & significant improvement in hemoglobin concentration, RBC indices like MCV, MCH in sickle cell disease patients with Hydroxyurea therapy.

Hydroxyurea is very effective drug for Sickle cell disease patients. Electrolytes like serum potassium level was significantly higher in the sickle cell disease patients without hydroxyurea therapy with compare to the sickle cell disease patients with hydroxyurea therapy & normal individuals.

The study had limitations sample size of the study was relatively small. In sickle cell disease patients hydroxyurea therapy significantly decreased the rate of transfusion & hospitalization.

Ethical approval: The study was approved by the Institutional ethical committee of Late Shri Lakhiram Agrawal Memorial Govt. Medical College Raigarh (C.G.)

Work attributed to: Sant Baba Guru Ghasidas Ji memorial Govt. Hospital associated Late Shri Lakhiram, Agrawal Memorial Govt. Medical College Raigarh (C.G.), India

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